

Archaeology and Memory, and the International Brigades, in a Battlescape of the Spanish Civil War

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Résumé : Archéologie et Mémoire : les Brigades Internationales sur fond de Guerre Civile Espagnole

Les Brigades Internationales durant la Guerre Civile Espagnole (GVE) sont bien connues pour tout ce qui est relatif à la géopolitique de l'entre-deux-guerres, à leur histoire et à leur constitution. En revanche, nous connaissons peu la matérialité des paysages dans lesquels les Brigadistes ont vécu, combattu et péri. Cet article, basé sur le travail de terrain effectué par l'*International Brigades Archaeology Project* (IBAP) en Espagne en 2014 et en 2015, vise à présenter quelques exemples de cette matérialité grâce à l'archéologie du paysage, ainsi qu'à travers l'expérience de volontaires étrangers ayant contribué à ce projet, certains de ces volontaires étant eux-mêmes des descendants des Brigadistes Internationaux. Le travail de terrain de l'IBAP a été mené au sud-est de Saragosse, autour des ruines de Belchite, icônes de la Guerre Civile, et le long des tranchées en direction du nord à Mediana de Aragón, où se sont opposés nationalistes. La réaction du conseil municipal et des habitants de Belchite ont fait également l'objet d'une discussion.

Mots-clefs : archéologie des conflits modernes, Guerre Civile Espagnole, archéologie du paysage

Abstract : A great deal is known about the International Brigades in the Spanish Civil War (SCW) in terms of inter-world war geopolitics, their history and make-up, but little is known about the materiality of the landscapes in which they lived, fought, and died. This paper, based on fieldwork carried out by the *International Brigades Archaeology Project* (IBAP) in Spain, in 2014 and 2015, aims to present examples of that materiality through landscape archaeology, and through the experiences of foreign volunteers on the project, some of which were related to International Brigaders. IBAP's fieldwork took place southeast of Zaragoza around the iconic Civil War ruins of Belchite, and along the opposing Nationalist and Republican entrenchments to the north, at Mediana de Aragón. The reaction of the town council and people of Belchite to the project is also discussed.

Keywords : Modern Conflict Archaeology, Spanish Civil War, Landscape Archaeology

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علم الآثار والذاكرة: الألوية الدولية على خلفية الحرب الأهلية الإسبانية

نحن نعرف الكثير عن الألوية الدولية في زمن الحرب الأهلية الإسبانية K وذلك فيما يتعلق بالجغرافيا السياسية العسكرية وتاريخهم ودستورهم، لكننا نعرف القليل عن الأهمية المادية للمشاهد الطبيعية التي عاش فيها اللواء، والتي قاتل فيها وهلك. تهدف هذه المقالة، المستندة إلى العمل الميداني الذي قام به مشروع آثار الألوية الدولي في إسبانيا بين عامي 2014 و 2015 إلى تقديم بعض الأمثلة من خلال علم آثار المشاهد الطبيعية وكذلك من خلال تجربة المتطوعين الأجانب الذين ساهموا في هذا المشروع. بعض هؤلاء المتطوعين هم أنفسهم من نسل اللواء الدولي. تركز العمل الميداني لمشروع آثار الألوية الدولي في جنوب شرق سرقسطة وحول أطلال بلدة بيلتشيقي، وأيقونات الحرب الأهلية، وعلى طول الخنادق التي تقابل القوميين والجمهوريين والتي تتجه شمالاً إلى مديانا أراغون. وتناقش أيضاً رد فعل المجلس البلدي وسكان بيلتشيقي.

الكلمات المفتاحية: آثار النزاعات الحديثة، الحرب الأهلية الإسبانية، علم آثار المشاهد الطبيعية.

ثانستي شويتهوار و ياده و هريه كان: ليواي تيوده و له تي له سهر باشماوهي جهنگي ناوخوي سباني

زورشت له سهر ليواي تيوده و له تي كاتي جهنگي ناوخوي سباني (GVE) سه بارهت به جوجرافياي سياسي و سه ربازي له تيوان ههردو ويكاندا ده زانين، وه سه بارهت به ميژوو و ده ستوريشيان، به لام له سهر گرنكي مدهي ديمهني سرروشي ته و كاتهي كهوا ليواكان تيادا ژيان و وه سه بارهت هب كوشتن و ويژانكردن. ته مانجي ته م بابه ته، پشتي به كاري ميداني پروژه ي ليواي شويته واري تيوده و له تي به ستوه له ئيسپانيا له سالاني 2014 و 2015 دا، بو پيشكش كدي هه ندي نمونه له سهر ته و گرينگيه له ماوهي زانستي شويته واري سرروشيته وه وه ههروه ها له رنگاي تاقيكر دنه وهي خيه خشانه وه كهوا به شداربوون له م پروژه يه دا، وه هه ندي له و خه لكي خو به خشانه ي كهوا به شداربوون له م ليوايه. كاري مهيداني IBAP له باشوري-روژه لاتي سه ره گوزه، له دوره ي باشماوهي گوندي بيلشيقي گونديكي بچووكي سهر به پاريزگاي سه ره گوزه ته نجمدرا، چاله كاني جهنگي ناوه خو، وه به دريزايه چاله كاني به رهه لستان و جمهوردا وه به رزيبونه وه به ره و باكوردا، تاوه كو شاري ميديانا ي تاراگون. كاردانه وهي ته نجومه ني شاره واوونو خه لكي بيلشيقي بابه تي گفتموگومان ده ييت. ووشه ي تپهر: شويته وار و ناكوكيه كاني نوي، جهنگي ناوخوي ئيسپانيا، ديمهني شويته واريه كان.

باستان شناسي و خاطره: تپهاي بين المللي در جنگ داخلي اسبانيا

ديريست در مورد تپهاي بين المللي در زمان جنگ داخلي اسبانيا² تاريخ و تشكيل و آنچه كه بين اين دو ژئوپوليتيك نظامي گذشته، آگاهيم؛ اما اندكي در مورد ماديت منظري، كه اين تپها در آن زندگي، جنگ و از بين رفته اند ميدانيم. اين مقاله به اساس كار ساحوي پروژه باستان شناسي تپهاي بين المللي³، بين سالهاي 2014-2015 ميلادي در اسبانيا انجام شده و با ارائه چندين مثال، بازگو كننده ماديت اين زمان است، كه از طريق باستان شناسي منظري و تجربه رضاكاران خارجي سيم درين پروژه حاصل گرديده. بعضي از خارجيهاي رضاكار از اولادههاي سربازان بين المللي اند. كار ساحوي پروژه باستان شناسي تپهاي بين المللي در جنوب شرق ساراگوسا در اطراف ويرانههاي بلچيته انجام شد. اين منطقه نماديست از جنگ داخلي اسبانيا، واقع در امتداد سنگري، كه ملي گرايان و جمهوري خواهان را دور هم قرار مي دهد و بطرف شمال تا مديانا داراگون ادامه دارد. عكس العمل شوراي شهري و شهروندان بلچيته نيز موضوع مورد بحث اين مقاله است. واژه هاي كليدي: تپهاي باستاني، اشغال نظامي، خسارات، تاثيرات، درگيريها، متدولوژي (روش شناسي).

2. GCE (Guerre Civile Espagnole).

3. IBAP (International Brigades Archaeology Project)

ARCHAEOLOGIES OF THE SPANISH CIVIL WAR

WHEN I first became interested in the archaeology of the Spanish Civil War, almost everyone I talked to about the work I was about to embark on, presumed that I was involved in field-work looking for, and examining and unearthing, sites of extra-judicial killings and burials from the Civil War and the post-war period of Francoist repression. Many crimes against humanity were carried out by both sides during the war, with an estimate of more than 49,000 unlawful killings carried out by supporters of the Republican government⁴, while the much greater estimate of up to 200,000 or more⁵ extra-judicial killings were carried out by Francoist Nationalist forces and their supporters, and the victorious Francoist regime after the war⁶. Many opponents of the Nationalist regime also spent much of the 1940s, and into the early 1950s, imprisoned or in concentration or labour camps⁷. The Francoist rebels who, on the 17th of July, 1936, attempted to depose Spain's democratically elected left-wing Popular Front government – which won the country's national elections just seven months previously – saw themselves as on a holy crusade – *La Cruzada Nacional* – to rid the country of what they saw as a surge of socialist and liberal democratic ideals and institutions, and to preserve the power and authority of the country's traditional elites: the landed classes, the moneyed oligarchies, the Catholic Church, and the Army⁸.

The victims and their families of that 'Crusade', and the families of those people killed in the Fascist repression that occurred in those parts of Spain occupied by the Nationalists early on, and throughout Spain after the war, stayed silent for the 36 years that the dictator Francisco Franco ruled the country. In fact, they stayed silent until the new millennium. At that time, the journalist Emilio Silva Barrera wanted to look for the remains of his own grandfather, and tell the story of the violence that occurred in his grandfather's village in northern Spain, and through his efforts with Santiago Macías and others, the *Aso-*

ciacion para la Recuperacion de la Memoria Historica, that is the *Association for the Recovery of Historical Memory* (the ARHM), was founded. The ARHM is a national organisation, now taking advantage of Spain's 'Historical Memory Law' of 2007 which reversed the so-called 'Pact of Silence' that sought, after the death of Franco in 1975, not to examine the legacy of the Spanish Civil War and the Franco Regime for the supposed fear of "raking up the ashes", and opening old wounds that would divide the country⁹.

With the right to examine the actions of the Franco regime and the events of the Civil War – supported by the Law of Historical Memory – the ARHM (and other similar organisations and interest groups of various kinds and sizes) has become a major catalyst in unearthing the injustices of the war, and its aftermath, by excavating many sites of extra-judicial and mass killings perpetrated by the Nationalists. As of 2015, more than 150 grave sites had been examined by the ARHM alone, and the remains of more than 1300 victims¹⁰ were exhumed. All of this has been carried out mainly by volunteers, alongside forensic archaeologists and anthropologists, and their work has allowed numerous Spanish families and communities to learn about the circumstances of the disappearance and death of their family and community members, and to achieve personal, familial, and community 'closure'. The ARHM is in itself a profound facilitator of this, and of bearing witness to and making sense of the violence of the Civil War. As an archaeological endeavour, their work, and that of their kindred organisations is poignant in the extreme.

There is, however, another type of archaeology that is taking place in Spain, and though for some it may seem overshadowed by the work of the ARHM, it too aims to make sense of the Spanish Civil War and its legacy, and it too bears 'witness' to the war and memorialises it. This is the archaeology dealt with in this paper, and it is the complex archaeology of modern 20th

4. PRESTON 2013, p. xvi.

5. BEEVOR 2006, p. 94 & 405.

6. The Francoists forces and supporters are also referred to as Nationalist, Rebels, or Fascists. Supporters of the elected Government of Spain are referred to as either Republicans or Loyalists. Francoists very often referred to Republicans as 'Reds' – categorizing all government supporters as 'Communists'.

7. GONZÁLEZ-RUIBAL 2011.

8. PRESTON 1993, p. 185 & 351.

9. PRESTON 2013, p. 520.

10. ALBA 2015.

and 21st century conflict. A popular view of conflict archaeology is battlefield archaeology, but there is a drastic difference between the two. Battlefield archaeology deals with a specific facet of conflict, and one that is only a part of the much broader field of conflict archaeology. In the main, it deals with the events and happenings of a single event in history – a single battle. This confines it spatially and temporally, and thereby differentiates it from the archaeology of conflict which is highly multidimensional.

Modern conflict can be military or civilian. It can include small-scale ethnic disputes or larger civil conflagrations. Conflicts can be ‘hot’ or ‘cold’ and spread across the globe. Their complexity and size can include individual battlefields, the landscapes in which battles are situated, and the ‘landscape of experience’, including not just the land, but also the sea and air, and into space¹¹. This sense of scale and multidimensionality, to Nicholas Saunders for instance, means that the archaeology of modern conflict is, by its very nature,

“an anthropologically-informed multidisciplinary endeavour, concerned with the social, cultural, psychological, and technological as well as military complexities of recent conflicts, and

their powerful and unpredictable legacies. . . This multitude of issues makes modern conflict sites, in effect, highly sensitised multilayered landscapes that require a robust, interdisciplinary approach, far beyond the ability of traditional, single event-oriented, battlefield archaeology to deliver”¹².

By taking this multidimensional approach conflict archaeology explores our relationship with the material transformations that inevitably come about through war. How landscapes change over time during conflicts, and how they affect the ways in which people work and act out their daily lives in their attempts to survive and make sense of the momentous events in which they either willingly, or unwillingly, are involved.

Such a recent or contemporary archaeology can draw upon people’s memories and experiences, so it can include oral history. It can draw upon documentary sources, and these can also include a great deal of audio and visual resources; and for the very contemporary world, it can draw upon the internet. As such, this type of archaeology brings to the fore memories as well as histories of recent conflicts, and by so doing, it also bears witness to them.

11. SCHOFIELD 2005, p. 19-20.

12. SAUNDERS 2012, p. x.

Figure 1: View of the ruins of Old Belchite. Photo: Óscar Rodríguez.

ARCHAEOLOGY AND MEMORY: THE INTERNATIONAL BRIGADES ARCHAEOLOGY PROJECT

The two World Wars make up the beginning and end of what some have called Europe's second Thirty Year's War¹³, and between them, and virtually on the eve of World War Two, and lasting from July 1936 to April 1939 was, the Spanish Civil War. Among the combatants of that war were the more than 35,000 volunteers from 50 some odd countries that made up the International Brigades fighting for the Spanish Republic. Although some have criticised the brigaders as a fighting force manipu-

lated by the Soviet Union and the *Communist International* (which founded the Brigades), over all, they are remembered as 'right thinking' individuals who recognised the threat of rising fascism in Europe, and felt they had to stop 'talking' about it and actually do something. To confront the threat and fight it in what was its latest battle ground – Spain¹⁴. This was a Democratic country with most of its military in revolt, and which was denied international aid by a Non-Intervention treaty that came

13. KERSHAW 2005.

14. The bibliography on the International Brigade is very large, with publications going back to the very end of the Civil War in 1939 (for example, see RUST 1939). However, for a very small selection of more recent publications relevant to this research, and importantly, utilizing records from the former Soviet Union, see BAXELL 2007, 2012; EBY 2007; PETROU 2008; SKOUTELSKY 1998.

15. Twenty-eight countries signed the non-intervention agreement that was put forward by France and 'strongly championed' by Great Britain. However, it was blatantly ignored, in the first instance, by Germany, Portugal, and Italy who supported the Nationalists, and then by

into effect soon after the start of the war, in August 1936¹⁵.

This sense of willingness on the part of the international volunteers to put their lives on the line, to fight for a cause: a cause that was politically to the left, and with an inherent sense of social, and politically social, justice and responsibility, has caused the brigaders to still be admired today, with International Brigade organisations in numerous countries aiming to keep alive their memory, and fostering the ideals that inspired the volunteers to go to Spain in the first place. As a result, there is today an international community of people keen to learn about the Brigades, and to spread 'the word' about the ideals that they see the brigaders as standing for. Some of these people

are politically active (usually on the left) while others are not. But they support the International Brigade organisations that exist in many countries, and may go to their sponsored events, and even go to Spain as individuals, or in groups, to visit the battle sites and tread where the men of the brigades lived, fought and died some eighty odd years ago.

The memories of individual brigaders, and the women and men who volunteered in other capacities or with the anti-fascist militias, are still kept alive by relatives of former volunteers, and through the efforts of battlefield tour guides who are extremely enthusiastic and knowledgeable about their subject. This very active interest, apparently alive in the activities of the Brigade

Figure 2: Map showing the position of Belchite and Mediana, and the Mediana Lines study area. The map also shows how the front line east of Zaragoza changed in the late Summer of 1937. Sources (main map):

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Batalla_de_Belchite_català.jpg; (inset map): <http://gta.wikia.com/wiki/File:Spain-Map.png>.

the Soviet Union which supported the Republic.

Figure 3: IBAP participants and visitors in 2014, outside the entrance to Old Belchite. Photo: Óscar Rodríguez.

organisations, and by individuals from many walks of life, inspired the creation of the International Brigades Archaeology Project in 2014 – IBAP.

By following the lead of those research projects that have explored the archaeology of World War One by drawing upon private individuals for support – often linked on a personal level through their own nation's connections with the Great War – it was thought that people from outside of Spain, with a strong and heartfelt interest in the International Brigades would be keen to know more about the Brigades through the very hands-on activity of archaeology. Through archaeology, they would have the chance to literally – intimately even – touch the past. All archaeology is forensic by nature, and as such, it bears witness to past human activities.

The model for IBAP was the Great Arab Revolt Project (GARP), which, between 2005 and 2014 excavated sites, and explored and surveyed landscapes of the First World War in southern Jordan with volunteers who paid to take part and, by doing so, contributed to the running and sustainability of the project¹⁶. Running research in the field in this way is not unusual, since many projects do not have enough funding to ei-

ther get started, or sustain themselves over a reasonable period of time. Archaeology in Spain dealing with the Spanish Civil War is also poorly funded, and many projects work very much on shoe string budgets with money cobbled together from a variety of sources. So, at an archaeological conference in Leicester (UK) in 2013, Alfredo González-Ruibal (of Incipit, the Heritage Sciences branch of the Spanish National Research Council¹⁷) and I talked about the possibility of a GARP-like project centering on the International Brigades in the Spanish Civil War, and subsequently IBAP was born. Alfredo González-Ruibal, as the project's lead archaeologist, had been working on Civil War archaeology since 2006, when he surveyed and excavated remains of the Civil War extant in Madrid's University City. He is a leading proponent of modern conflict archaeology, and continues to work on many battle arenas and places of violence in Spain. He also works with a dedicated team of Spanish archaeologists, all with a strong interest in the archaeology of modern conflict.

Alfredo González-Ruibal was keen to start the project since, with his many years experience, he thought it would be more than worthwhile to investigate a conflict landscape through the prism of the International Brigades. So through

16. Website for the project is <http://www.jordan1914-18archaeology.org/>. Accessed 6 April 2018.

17. Website for Incipit (CSIC) is <http://www.incipit.csic.es/en/Default.aspx>. Accessed 6 April 2018.

the research interests of a colleague based in Zaragoza, the town of Belchite – one of the most iconic locations of the Civil War which was bitterly fought over in both 1937 and 1938, and whose ruinous remains (Figure 1) are preserved as a memorial to the conflict – was chosen as the locus for IBAP's fieldwork¹⁸.

Work at Belchite itself was limited to field walking just outside the ruined town's boundaries, but excavations and surveys were carried out in the countryside nearby, and 17 kilometres to the north near the village of Mediana de Aragón (Mediana, Figure 2). The project had mixed funding from Spanish (and EU) sources, supplemented by the paying volunteers (along with a small amount of money from the UK in 2015). The project's field seasons were of two week's duration, similar to those of GARP.

In the two years that IBAP was in existence, there were no more than 11 volunteers per season, though the full compliment of fieldworkers could double with Alfredo González-Ruibal's professional staff and Spanish students (Figure 3).

Most of the volunteers came out for the full two weeks, while some only participated for one week. The age range varied from 21 to 74, and the mix included individuals from Britain, Canada, Ireland, The United States and Croatia, as well as some Spanish paying volunteers. Recently graduated archaeologists and post-graduates took part, as well as individuals with no experience of archaeology but with a keen interest in the Spanish Civil War, and in particular, the International Brigades. The volunteers included people who knew brigaders personally, but more especially, we had volunteers who were actual relatives of International Brigaders. For this latter group (though they only participated in 2014), taking part in IBAP was very much a personal journey, one in which they could get close to the very earth on which their uncles, fathers and grandfathers fought, and for some, died. They wished to gain an extra dimension to the memory of their relatives, who to them, were people who were very special indeed.

The father of one American volunteer was a Cypriot, who served with the 15th International Brigade as an interpreter and driver. Another woman, from Glasgow, never got to know her grandfather because he died in the war along the Aragón front when her own father was only twelve. He was one of the few brigaders with a family, since men with wives and children were often discouraged from joining-up. But his memory lived on in his letters sent home, and many of his accounts were in-

cluded in the book *Homage to Caledonia*¹⁹, about the volunteers from Scotland. Strikingly, two Anglo-American sisters joined the project, and they had an uncle, Sidney Shostek (adjutant to the American officer Robert Merriman) who died at Belchite (Figure 4). While on the project, and for a short while afterwards, they kept up a blog about their experiences and feelings while working in and around Belchite:

“Belchite was a name familiar to our family for many years as the place where our uncle Sidney Shostek died. We made up our stories based on the few scraps left to us; a newspaper article, a few pages of diary, a letter. We made assumptions which [once taking part in IBAP and reading the Merriman diaries] we had to discard: Sidney buried in the olive press; leaving roses at the town fountain. We imagined a scenario where Sidney walked through the town gate, following a tank, and was shot from the church tower.

“Now we learned that the Lincoln Battalion approached the fascist holdout in the church from the opposite side of town. We saw the building used first as a hospital, then as the Falangist headquarters. This was where a fascist prisoner was leading a tank, followed by Sidney, when he was shot in the head from a high vantage point. It was clear that this must have been either the clock tower, or one of the buildings near it”²⁰.

While working around and exploring Belchite, the sisters, Elaine and Wendy, came face to face with the place of death, the street even, where their uncle was killed. As their blog testifies, they came to an appreciation of the materiality of the battle-spaces of the Civil War. They could see the remains of grenades, bullets and cartridges, all of mixed variety – especially for the Republican troops – and they could handle the flesh tearing shrapnel that litters any modern battlefield. And in the case of the fought over landscape around Belchite, they came to feel the dust and heat of the so-called desert of Aragón. Again, as they wrote in their blog:

“the positions of the finds we had marked were recorded calling out to a staffer with a transom on the next hill. Elaine was astonished at the detail of data: identifying each tiny piece of metal, each twist of wire... and giving it a number and location. Meanwhile Wendy was sweating at the top of the hill, cheerfully shoveling, carefully scraping in a trench, volunteers calling out for an identification when they found something they hoped was of interest.

“Elaine was amazed that such seemingly unimportant ob-

18. GONZÁLEZ-RUIBAL *et al.* 2015; RODRÍGUEZ SIMÓN *et al.* 2016.

19. GRAY 2008.

20. LEWIS & RYAN 2014.

jects could tell archaeologists a story: Russian bullets from 1917, German machine gun casings, a jug, ammunition boxes and unexploded mortars.

“Through repetitive work in the sun and dust personal and national histories are uncovered. An International Brigader from Wales, Alun Menai Williams, was asked: What was Spain like? He replied, ‘I can’t tell you- I only know the taste of the soil when you have your nose six inches from the ground, crawling’. But modern scientific techniques help put all the little pieces together for a view a little further off the ground”²¹.

Nevertheless, the sisters also found joy in their encounter with the remains of war. Being keen and relatively accomplished amateur singers they would break into song in the streets of Belchite, singing *The Communist International* and *Viva La Quince Brigada*, but when standing in the ruins of one of Belchite’s churches, the sisters had this to say in their blog:

“Near here, German planes had flattened many houses. We sang ‘*Gebat hob ikh a heym*’, a deeply felt [Yiddish] song of loss of home, written in the ruins of the Warsaw Ghetto.

‘Once I had a home to comfort me.. the years I spent to build it, in one breath, to rubble smashed... in a moment’s time’²².

To the sisters, and this is true of the other IBAP participants who were related to Brigaders, their uncle was always somewhere in the background of their lives, and his convictions and desire to make the world a better place served, in their own words, as a real model for them.

In 2015, another volunteer, but one not related to any brigader, Geoffrey Billett, wrote about his involvement on the project. He is also a gifted photographer, and he published his impressions and some photographs in an online magazine: *Bizaare Culture*. His background was in psychiatric nursing and he had no previous exposure to archaeology save for the television programme *Time Team*. He was profoundly struck by our archaeological confrontation with a relatively recent and violent past, describing archaeology as a “rabbit hole, into a dimension of reversed-engineered history”. His photos capture the ghost-like quality of ruined, Old Belchite, initially preserved by Franco as a memorial testifying to the brutality of “the Reds”, and barely separated from the New Town which

Figure 4: Elaine Ryan in the ruins of Old Belchite. She is holding a photograph of her uncle killed when the International Brigades took the town in 1937. Photo: Álvaro Minguito.

21. LEWIS & RYAN 2014.

22. LEWIS & RYAN 2014.

was constructed by forced labour in the 1950s. In the materiality of the two towns, one a ghost town while the other an exemplar of fascist town planning in a rural setting, he saw continued conflict. And in this landscape of conflict he saw, in his words, “young intellectuals [archaeologists] try[ing] to make sense of – and undo – a wrong which stubbornly, at least in Spain, remains unyielding to science or reason”²³.

But this tension, this conflict, this wrong that refuses to go away, had an impact on the other members of IBAP too, and it was in a real and concrete way. In 2014, the Belchite town council supported our fieldwork wholeheartedly. They provided a flat, for free, for the professional Spanish archaeologists on the project, and they provided an earth moving machine as well, at no cost. They also facilitated the project by providing an assembly room so that two public presentations could be given to the local community. In the first talk, Alfredo González-Ruibal introduced the project to the people attending, and he explained our fieldwork interests and intentions. At the end of the season, he gave another presentation, summarising and presenting our findings. In both instances, the townsfolk welcomed us and were very keen to see us get on with our work. They too wanted us to undo a wrong which stubbornly remains unyielding to science or reason.

There was, however, a little bit of opposition. In Alfredo González-Ruibal's first presentation, he received heckling from a man in the back of the hall. The other people, in no uncertain terms told him to keep quiet, but it turned out, as I was told, that he was the son of a man who was known to be the head of a death squad in the Belchite area, after the war. We saw him later in the street, and if looks could kill, then we would have ended up like the victims of his father. Of course, this should not have been a surprise. There were still Fascist emblems affixed to buildings in Belchite, and it is not uncommon to find present day pro-fascist graffiti. Even in the nearby village of Codo where the IBAP volunteers were housed in 2014, there was a street named after General Franco.

Nonetheless, our relations with the community of Belchite and its town council were extremely good, and we were under the impression that their goodwill and support would continue. But in the Spring of 2015, there were regional elections in Spain,

and the local town council was won by the conservative, *Partido Popular* (the Popular Party – the PP) and with a new PP mayor our fortunes were to change.

First it took longer than it did in 2014, to secure agreements with the town council and with the Aragónese government for our September fieldwork. The town council did provide the same flat as in the previous year, but after one week in the field, the Mayor evicted the Spanish team (with no warning and with no clear reason), and this meant that we had to find extra accommodation in a single day. Also, the council did not provide any earth moving machinery as in the previous year, and we had to find and pay for our own. Unlike in 2014, the council did not publicise our work, and they did not give us space for any public presentations in the town hall. We ended up giving only one public presentation at the end of the season, and that was in a much smaller venue within Belchite's ethnographic museum. We had open days on site (as in the previous season), and although our publicity did not match that of 2014, we still had a good turnout from local people.

In Alfredo González-Ruibal's public presentation at the end of the 2015 season, we had very positive feedback from the people who attended. Unlike, presumably, the mayor (and other PP members), they thought that our explorations of the warscape around Belchite very worthwhile indeed. And although we excavated trenches and bunkers, and the former do not preserve well once exposed, they wanted to know why was there not more work like ours, and why were the sites that we investigated not preserved. They clearly did not want to keep the history of the Civil War under wraps. Indeed, some even demanded that this recent archaeology be preserved for all to see. Unfortunately, we had to reply that, firstly, Civil War remains are not commonly treated as “archaeology” in Spain since they are not more than 100 years old, and secondly, the money is just not available. Also, we reiterated that quite simply, we were no longer getting popular support from the Belchite Town Council. Of course, those who came to our presentations were people who deliberately felt that the nation's trauma from the Francoist years should be laid bare, while those people still dreaming of a Spain, where the stones of the country's past should not be upturned, stayed away and ignored us.

23. BILLETT 2015.

Figure 5: Military sketch map showing the Republican positions along the Mediana Lines as of September 4th, 1937. Source: Diario de Operaciones Belchite del 27-8-37 a 17-9-37, p. 25.

WARSCAPE ARCHAEOLOGY

Belchite was fortified by the Francoists early on in the Civil War. It was a part of the front line between them and the Republicans in the region of Aragón. When the Republic launched its Aragón offensive in the late Summer of 1937, Belchite was deemed a target that had to be occupied to secure the way to Zaragoza. The spearhead of the attack was carried out by the Dimitrov and Abraham Lincoln battalions of the 15th International Brigade. The fighting was severe and bloody and at the end of it, after a week or so, a third of the town was destroyed and left in ruins. The town was retaken by the Francoists in March of 1938, and that damaged the town even further.

Soon afterwards, Belchite was seen as a monument to the “martyrdom of Aragónese villages” : the martyrdom of Catholic and Nationalist Spain, suffered at by the hands of the “barbaric” and “destructive” – “Reds”, meaning the Repub-

lican government. As such, the ruins of the town were deemed by Franco and the Nationalist regime to be a “precious monument and sanctuary of patriotism for future generations”. The ruins of the town would serve as a place to teach a new, Francoist, “national spirit” to the youth of the Nation²⁴. A new Francoist planned town was built alongside the ruins of the old town – similar to other planned towns in fascist and authoritarian countries elsewhere in Europe – though over time Old Belchite became even more ruinous by the robbing of building materials by the local people. Now, in democratic Spain, the ruined town is seen as a monument to all of the violence of the Civil War, and the town is a managed site with access only through guided walks.

However, since the subject of the Civil War is still contentious in Spain, and since the more pedestrian issues of health

24. GARCIA ENQUITA 2014.

and safety would have been difficult to manage within the ruins of Old Belchite, IBAP's fieldwork was directed into the *Campo de Belchite*, the countryside surrounding the town, and it included field walking and excavations of nearby Nationalist positions (and a partial survey of tunnels making up a part of Republican hill-top fortifications overlooking Belchite). But fur-

ther north of Belchite, by around 17 kilometres, and along the Mediana-Belchite road (now the A222), lies the Mediana system of entrenchments – the Mediana Lines – representing the front line created after the fall of Belchite to Republican forces in September 1937. Figure 5 is a contemporary military sketch map showing the positions occupied by Republican forces along the

Legend

Mediana Survey Areas 2014-15

- Survey Areas
- Survey Areas of fighting and habitation features

Nationalist and Republican Trenches in Survey Areas

- Communication Trenches
- Fire Trenches

Opposing Frontlines

- Nationalist Front
- Republican Front
- Support Trenches
- Trenches outside of Survey Areas

Figure 6: Map showing the fieldwork zones where excavations and surveys were undertaken by IBAP in 2014 and 2015. The two survey zones, where fighting positions and soldiers' habitations (shelters) were recorded, are highlighted.

Figure 7: Map showing a part of the so-called 'Parapet of Death' where Republican troops got their closest to the Fascist lines. Fire (fighting) trenches, communication trenches and support trenches are also indicated.

Figure 8: Map showing the disposition of Republican and Nationalist fighting positions along the opposing front lines at the 'Parapet of Death'.

Legend

- | | | |
|----------------------------------|--------------------------|-------------------------|
| ● Nationalist soldiers' shelters | ■ Communication Trenches | — 1937 Tracks as mapped |
| ● Republican soldiers' shelters | ■ Fire Trenches | --- Valley route-ways |
| --- Nationalist Front | ■ Support Trenches | |
| --- Republican Front | | |

Figure 9: Map showing the distribution and depth of soldiers' habitation structures – shelters and the like – behind the opposing front lines. It also shows the tracks behind the lines and the valley route-ways leading, in particular, to the Nationalist positions.

new front line at Mediana²⁵. Here, both the Nationalist and Republican armies dug-in, creating not just fighting spaces, but a landscape of settlement in what is now a relatively well preserved warscape.

As such, further locations were chosen for small scale and targeted excavations of mainly Republican features, which included a forward fighting machine gun position; a small dugout shelter suitable for one or two soldiers and linked by trenches to the machine gun post; a free standing pastoral shed-like structure that was re-used as a substantial shelter for Republican soldiers; semi-dugout shelters with dry stone walling, disposed along the slopes of a steep sided valley; and one, very small Na-

tionalist fighting position²⁶.

Fieldwalking aimed at recording the spread of battle debris was also carried out, while a further survey was undertaken to record the make-up and extent of the fighting lines and that of the soldiers' areas of habitation – the settlements, albeit martial ones – in the rear of both the Nationalist and Republican entrenchments. Some of the results of this latter work are described below.

Figure 6 indicates the overall area where IBAP undertook its excavations and surveys along the Mediana lines north of Belchite in 2014 and 2015, and the overall disposition of the Francoist and Republican trenches in the survey areas. The location,

25. ANONYM. 1937.

26. GONZÁLEZ-RUIBAL *et al.* 2015; RODRÍGUEZ SIMÓN *et al.* 2016.

close to the village of Mediana de Aragón includes a salient in the Francoist lines known as the 'Parapet of Death'. At this location, while Belchite was under siege by Republican forces, the British Battalion of the 15th International Brigade spent three to four days preventing a Nationalist counter attack by advancing through hastily excavated entrenchments to around 40 metres from the enemy lines. As an eye witness from the 15th Brigade wrote:

"The fighting at Mediana was not heavy but the whole experience was wearying and nerve-racking. The sleep-starved men had to be always on the alert against surprise attacks in a wide sector that was but thinly held by a depleted Battalion; for three days and nights, the Republican troops were subjected to a continuous aerial and artillery bombardment; twice they had to repulse night attacks and there was much skirmishing between the rival outposts which in some cases were only forty yards apart. In addition, there were terrific electric storms which, during the night, illuminated the country for miles around. But the men stuck it out and got down to the monotonous work of constructing fortifications with a right good-will, and with such success that the casualties were only slight"²⁷.

Figure 7 shows the very spot where the Brigaders got to within "forty yards" (or metres) of the Nationalist trenches. But a plot like this, showing just the opposing Nationalist and Republican trenches, does not illustrate the built environment or the 'architecture' of the trenches.

In Figure 8 you can see the distribution of fighting positions along the trenches at the 'Parapet of Death', as surveyed in 2014 and 2015. On the other hand, in Figure 9, you can see the depth of occupation, by both the Republican and the Francoist forces, well behind the support and communication trenches, and which extend for more than half a kilometre behind (for

example) the Nationalist front line defences (Figure 9). The terrain in this area is highly interdigitated, and the recorded habitation features – soldiers' shelters – which number in total more than 700 in the survey areas, are mainly situated in the numerous steep sided valleys which served as linkages or route-ways with the fighting trenches along the front.

Most of the features are poorly preserved, but examples of some of the Nationalist habitations and trenches can be seen in Figure 10 and Figure 11. Further, similar shelters, both dug-out and built-up with dry stone walling, are also situated in steep sided valleys behind the Republican lines, though overall, the Republican trenches and concentrated living areas are more spread out than the Nationalist ones. Nevertheless, in an area we dubbed 'Little Gallipoli', because of the density of shelters constructed in levels, one above another, we found dense concentrations of shelters in obvious tiers, situated in steep, hillside embayments (Figure 12). When I revisited the Mediana lines in the Summer 2017, I found further locations where Republican trenches and shelters were disposed, again in tiers, but this time they were spread out east of the Mediana-Belchite road – the A222.

The Republican lines at Mediana were over run by the Nationalist army in March of 1938, but for the six months previously, the two opposing armies faced each other off and built communities which had specific zones for living as well as fighting, and all connected through link-ways in the rear that were either valley bottoms or communication trenches. The opposing front lines throughout Spain, in that country's brutal Civil War, as in all wars, were not just places of fighting. They were places where soldiers dwelled, and their make up and disposition, and their individual structures, reflected the different components of any settlement, martial or otherwise.

27. RUST 1939, p. 94.

Figure 10: View behind the Nationalist lines along the 'Parapet of Death'. It shows a communication trench, a cluster of soldiers' dugout shelters, and a linking, valley route-way. The Nationalist front is to the left, beyond the limit of the photograph.

Figure 11: Four views of Nationalist trenches and soldiers' dugout shelters. Photos A and B show shelters dug into hillsides outlining the steep valleys behind the front lines. They are well made, incorporating stone rubble walls. Photo C shows Nationalist trenches in the rear. The one in the foreground is part of a support area, while the trench in the distance is a communication trench heading towards the front lines. In the middle of the photo is a terraced footpath with shelters dug out along it. Photo D shows a part of the Nationalist front line trenches.

Figure 12: View of a part of 'Little Gallipoli'. An area of dugout and well made, rubble walled shelters, built in tiers along the steep side of a valley in the Republican rear.

CONCLUSION

While working near and around Belchite, one of Spain's most iconic sites of memory of the Spanish Civil War, The International Brigades Archaeology Project (IBAP) was able to involve private individuals from a number of countries with a sincere interest in Spain's Civil War, and perhaps more crucially, to even involve participants related to former International Brigade volunteers. The confrontation of these individuals with the materiality of the battlespaces where their relations fought, and in some instances died, had a profound effect on them and the project as a whole. It turned IBAP into a community archaeology project, but one with a community that was international. This undoubtedly added an extra dimension to the work undertaken by the project, and illustrates that the multi-dimensional nature of modern conflict archaeology applies also to the participants in the field, as well as the complex landscapes upon which wars are fought.

The so-called desert of Aragón was the setting of IBAP's landscape investigations, and these exposed a martial landscape that was lived in as well as fought over, with a network of fighting zones, trenches, route-ways and linkages, and habitation areas. The latter, consisting of shelters dug out of the ground or built up with dry stone walling, by either individuals or groups

of soldiers, showed a density of occupation that was not initially envisaged. They were a backdrop to the fighting trenches at Mediana, where the Republican lines, manned by the 15th International Brigade, came as close as forty meters to the Francoist entrenchments.

IBAP also aimed to involve the local people of Belchite through site visits and public presentations. But even in these instances, the memory and scars of the Civil War that still rack Spanish society came to the fore. There was animosity from some modern-day pro-Francoists, and when the political complexion of the town council changed as a result of recent local elections, the assistance given to the project in its first year was discontinued. This illustrated the highly sensitive nature of our fieldwork, and shows that archaeologists of all recent conflicts do more than just expose historical remains and weave a narrative from them.

As all archaeologists know, fieldwork is physically demanding, and we struggle with the dust, the terrain, and the weather. But in Spain, by bearing witness to the Civil War through our work, and in effect memorialising it, we become part of another contemporary conflict – one that is ever present, and socially and politically charged.

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